

A LAYERED-SHELL MODEL OF ISOTROPIC COMPOSITES
WITH EXACT EXPRESSIONS FOR THE EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES

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Abstract:

A family of models, for multicomponent, isotropic mixtures, is suggested and discussed for which the exact values of the effective, linear-response constants can be calculated: The basic unit of the model is a hollow system of contacting concentric shells, each of which is made of one of the components. Space is packed with such units of different sizes, but the same proportions; the cavity within each such shell system is then packed with similar systems, and this continues in an infinite nesting sequence. We deal with the general case of a linear-response phenomenon involving n coupled driving fields; the effective response matrix is given in a closed form as a function of the volume fractions and the response matrices of the components. Some sub-families are treated in more detail. For example, a two-shell two-phase family spanned by q , volume fraction of the shells within the sphere they define. The special case $q=1$ is the well-known coated-sphere model. Varying q between zero and one, we get exact models that cover the whole range of allowed values of the effective constant of any isotropic composite. Another special case of interest is $1 \gg q$ (very thin shells). The value of the effective response matrix, L , is derived for this model, for a multicomponent mixtures; this turns out to have a simple form. The response matrix is symmetric under the interchange of any two components. This thin-shell model is an automatically isotropized laminate.

I. INTRODUCTION

The role of specific models in the study of the effective linear-response properties of multicomponent composites is two-fold: (i) They provide estimators of the effective properties of composites. (ii) More importantly, they serve as testing grounds for various general ideas that pertain to such composites; in particular, they help one assay the strengths of various bounds that one can derive, on the effective properties, from general arguments¹⁻¹⁰. Some of these models—such as the coated-sphere model—actually serve to delineate bounds of some significance¹. To cope with the ever-increasing sophistication of the bounds one is usually forced to employ solvable models of equal involvement; notably, hierarchical models of different degrees^{11,8,12}.

We add to the library of exactly solvable models, a family of simple models of composites that is, however, rather rich, and may serve as an additional test-bed, in the

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light of which one can consider the effective properties of composites. The models involve hollow multilayered spherical shells that fill space and which are filled from within, by similar shells-not, necessarily concentrically-in an infinite sequence of nesting. As they stand, the models are non-hierarchical, but, clearly, they may be incorporated into sundry hierarchical models.

All the results are derived for the general case of linear-response to n coupled driving fields, such as in the thermoelectric and magnetoelectric effects, or coupled multispecies diffusion. To our knowledge, there are no exact model-results, in the literature, for the coupled, multifield case.

The model is described in §II, where we also state the results for the single-field case. In §III we give the general formalism for calculating the effective response matrix for the general, multifield and multicomponent case. Section IV specializes to two-component models. In §V we show how working in the eigenbasis of fields, that can be defined for two-phase mixtures, one greatly facilitates the handling of this case. Further miscellaneous points are made in §VI.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE MODEL-THE SINGLE-FIELD CASE

The basic element of the model is a hollow, d -dimensional sphere that is made of p concentric shells, S_k , bounded by radii r_{k-1} and r_k ; $k=1, \dots, p$ (see Fig. 1). The shell S_k is filled with component k having a response coefficient value ϵ_k . This coefficient can represent the dielectric constant, the magnetic permeability, the electric- or heat-conductivity, or the like. The volume fraction of component k is thus

$$v_k = \frac{r_k^d - r_{k-1}^d}{r_p^d - r_0^d}; \quad \left(\sum_{k=1}^p v_k = 1 \right). \quad (1)$$

This shell system is also characterized by the volume fraction of the sphere occupied by the components: $q = (r_p^d - r_0^d) / r_p^d$. Imagine now that the hollow within r_0 is filled with a trial equivalent medium of coefficient ϵ and the whole sphere is embedded in the same medium. Can a value of ϵ be chosen such that the embedded sphere will not make itself felt outside; namely, that an externally applied field \vec{E}_0 will induce a displacement $\vec{D} = \epsilon \vec{E}_0$, outside?

If this is possible, we can construct a composite of the p components that will have ϵ as its exact effective coefficient: As shown in Fig. 2, in the first stage one fills space with shell systems, like that described above, with different sizes but the same proportions; the hollows within these systems are then filled-in a second nesting stage-with similar systems; continuing in this vein, in an infinite but converging nesting procedure, the whole volume of space is filled with the components. After the ℓ 'th nesting stage, a fraction $1 - (1-q)^\ell$ of space is filled with the components. The resulting composite has isotropic linear-response properties, by construction, with $\epsilon(\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_p, q)$.

This model takes a step beyond the multicoated-sphere model, in that the equivalent medium is both inside and outside the basic unit of layered shells. The resulting equation for the effective coefficient is then quadratic instead of linear. Further steps in this direction are not possible; for example, there is no equivalent medium in the case of a basic unit made of spaced-out concentric shells.

We defer the derivation of the expression for ϵ to §III where a formalism is described and the effective coefficients are derived, for the more general problem of coupled multifield phenomena. Here we only describe the procedure-as an introduction to the

more general problem-and give the results for the single-field case. We seek field configurations whereby the driving field outside the single shell system is homogeneous and hence derivable from a potential $\varphi(\vec{r}) = \phi(r)\cos\theta$ where r and θ are polar coordinates; the potential must have the same θ -dependence all over the system. Within each shell, $\varphi(\vec{r})$ satisfies the Laplace equation and thus $\phi(\vec{r})$ must then be of the form

$$\phi(r) = a_k r + \hat{b}_k r^{-(d-1)}; \quad r_{k-1} \leq r \leq r_k. \quad (2)$$

Here $k=0, \dots, p+1$ with $r_{-1}=0$, and r_{p+1} arbitrary but larger than r_p ; d is the dimension of the problem. We require a homogeneous field outside the outermost shell, i.e. $\hat{b}_{p+1} = 0$; we also require $\hat{b}_0 = 0$, lest the field diverge at $r = 0$; this leaves us with $2p+2$ unknowns. These are determined by the requirements that ϕ and $\frac{d\phi}{dr}$ be continuous across the $p+1$ boundaries r_0, \dots, r_p . A homogeneous set of linear equations is obtained whose coefficients depend on $\epsilon, \epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_p, v_1, \dots, v_p, q$ and a solution exists only when the determinant (of rank $2p+2$) of coefficients vanishes—a requirement that constitutes the (quadratic) equation for ϵ .

In §III we shall give a method, for calculating ϵ , that avoids such large determinants. Here we give the equation for ϵ for the two-component case:

$$v_1 \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1)(\epsilon + d'\epsilon_1)}{\epsilon_1} + v_2 \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_2)(\epsilon + d'\epsilon_2)}{\epsilon_2} + \frac{qv_1 v_2}{\epsilon_1 \epsilon_2 d} (d'\epsilon_2 + \epsilon)(d'\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2)(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon) - \frac{qv_2^2}{\epsilon_2} (\epsilon - \epsilon_2)(d'\epsilon_2 + \epsilon) = 0, \quad (3)$$

where component 2 is on the outside, and

$$d' \equiv d-1. \quad (4)$$

The field inside the cavity, while homogeneous, is not the same as that outside. the shielding factor $\sigma \equiv a_0/a_{p+1}$ is—as we were able to show—not larger than unity. Thus, in the complete model—medium, the field within a shell ℓ -times-nested, is reduced by a factor of at least σ^ℓ compared with the field outside the shells.

Given two components, the layered-shell models we construct from them by varying q from zero to unity, and allowing either component to fill the inner shell, cover the whole range of allowed value of the effective coefficient ϵ for any possible (isotropic) composite of the two materials.

To demonstrate this useful fact we first consider the limit of very thin shells: $q \rightarrow 0$. In this limit, eq. (3) approaches:

$$v_1 \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1)(\epsilon + d'\epsilon_1)}{\epsilon_1} + v_2 \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_2)(\epsilon + d'\epsilon_2)}{\epsilon_2} = 0, \quad (5)$$

by which ϵ is symmetric under the interchange $v_1 \leftrightarrow v_2, \epsilon_1 \leftrightarrow \epsilon_2$ (amounting to an interchange of the two shells while they retain their volumes). Such symmetric composites have attracted much interest¹³. A celebrated symmetric estimator is given by the coherent potential approximation^{14,15}. It is also known that the bounds on the allowed values of ϵ are materialized for the two coated sphere models (our $q = 1$ case) with component 1 or 2 on the outside. Thus, starting with one component on the outside and

$q=1$, we lower q to zero; then, interchanging the two shells we leave ϵ intact; then we increase q to unity again (the volume fractions remaining the same all along). In the process we change ϵ continuously from one bound to the opposite; thus covering the whole allowed range.

Equation (5) provides a symmetric estimator of the effective coefficient of composites and is straightforwardly generalized to the case of p components:

$$\sum_{k=1}^p v_k \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_k)(\epsilon + d' \epsilon_k)}{\epsilon_k} = 0 \quad (6)$$

This follows as a special case of a result we derive in § III and is quite unavoidable once we know that eq. (6) holds for two components.

Equation (6) can also be written as

$$\epsilon^2 \epsilon_h^{-1} + (d-2)\epsilon - (d-1)\epsilon_m = 0, \quad (7)$$

where ϵ_m and ϵ_h are, respectively, the mean and harmonic mean of the ϵ_k 's:

$$\epsilon_m \equiv \sum_{k=1}^p v_k \epsilon_k, \quad \epsilon_h \equiv \left(\sum_{k=1}^p v_k \epsilon_k^{-1} \right)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

The fact that ϵ depends on the ϵ_k 's and v_k 's only through ϵ_m and ϵ_h is quite natural; after all, the local geometry, in any small neighborhood of a point, is that of a plane laminate (for the thin-shells limit). For planar laminates, the effective coefficient is ϵ_m , when the field is parallel to the plane, and ϵ_h when it is perpendicular. The thin-shell geometry combines the two with weights that depend on the dimensionality of the problem: For $d=1$ we have $\epsilon = \epsilon_h$; for a very large d one has $\epsilon \rightarrow \epsilon_m$; in two dimensions (parallel cylindrical shells) we have the compact expression $\epsilon = (\epsilon_m \epsilon_h)^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

In three dimensions, the physical (positive) solution is

$$\epsilon = \frac{\epsilon_h}{2} \left(\sqrt{1 + 8 \epsilon_m / \epsilon_h} - 1 \right). \quad (9)$$

This result is closely related to one obtained by Schulgasser¹⁶ for a model of isotropized polycrystalline powders (made of a single material). Beginning with a uniaxial material with a response tensor $\text{diag}(\epsilon_{\perp}, \epsilon_{\perp}, \epsilon_{\parallel})$ Schulgasser forms homogeneous spheres made of crystal grains, with their symmetry axis along the radius of the sphere. A space that is filled with such spheres acts as an isotropic medium with an effective

$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\parallel} (\sqrt{1 + 8 \epsilon_{\perp} / \epsilon_{\parallel}} - 1) / 2$. The connection with eq. (9)-pointed out by Schulgasser himself-comes about thus: If in our layered-shell model we choose among the many schemes of nesting, the one shown in Fig. 3 whereby the nesting is always concentric, we obtain a space that is filled with similar spheres; these are much like the spheres used by Schulgasser in his model with the role of ϵ_{\parallel} , ϵ_{\perp} played by our ϵ_h, ϵ_m .

Hence, the three-dimensional, thin-shell model with concentric nesting is a special case of Schulgasser's isotropized polycrystalline powder. On the other hand, our results for arbitrary nesting schemes can be used to enlarge the class of models for which Schulgasser's result for polycrystals applies: It is plain to see that if shells of arbitrary thicknesses, and not necessarily of the same proportions, are prepared from radially aligned grains of a uniaxial crystal, and these are nested in an arbitrary

fashion, the resulting medium will still have the effective constant value given by Schulgasser's expression. One way to see this is to observe that we can take ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 such that their mean equals ϵ_{\perp} and their harmonic mean equals ϵ_{\parallel} of the crystal.

For any polycrystalline construction as described above, there is an equivalent thin-shells composite for which is given by eq. (9); independent of the nesting scheme of such a composite. It is true that if $\epsilon_{\perp} < \epsilon_{\parallel}$ we cannot find such a physical composite that is equivalent to the polycrystalline powder-for $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2 \geq 0$ we always have $\epsilon_m \geq \epsilon_h$ -but we can find, even in this case, unphysical ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 , one of which is negative, and v_1, v_2 such that $\epsilon_h \geq \epsilon_m \geq 0$ and our derivation goes through, formally, in this case too. At any rate, we verified this by a direct calculation of the effective ϵ for a shell of arbitrary proportions.

we now turn briefly to the case where one of the components has a vanishing, or an infinite constant. For example, when ϵ stands for the electric conductivity, these correspond to an insulator and a superconductor, respectively. When $\epsilon_2 = 0$, the only non-negative solution of eq. (3) is $\epsilon = 0$; clearly no conduction is possible when all the spheres are coated by an insulator on the outside. When $\epsilon_1 = 0$ we get

$$\epsilon = \frac{v_2 q d'}{d - v_2 q} \epsilon_2; \quad (10)$$

the conductivity is finite for a finite value of q but goes to zero with q even though the volume fraction is finite. The reason for this behavior is that only the outer shell in the un-nested systems contribute to the conductivity-as the inner, insulating shell isolates all that is nested within this primary shell. The medium acts then as as if the volume fraction of the conductor is only $q v_2$. When one of the components is superconducting, if it is the outer component, ϵ_2 , the only non-negative solution is an infinite ϵ . When ϵ_1 is infinite we get

$$\frac{d - q v_2 d'}{q v_2} \epsilon_2. \quad (11)$$

So far we have discussed a one-parameter family of two-shell, two-phase models. More involved two-phase models can be obtained by arranging the two components in more than two alternating shells. Consider, for example, a three-shell configuration in which the first and third shells contain component 1 and the intermediate shell contains component 2. Fixing q and the volume fractions, the fraction, s , of the volume of component 1 that is in the inner shell ($0 \leq s \leq 1$) constitute a second parameter: $\epsilon = (\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, v_1, v_2, q, s)$. At the same time we want to consider a similar composite with component 2 divided between the first and third shell, and s now measuring the fraction of 2 in the third shell; for this $\epsilon = \hat{\epsilon}(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, v_1, v_2, q, s)$. For $s = 0$ and $s = 1$ we get the restricted family discussed before, and $\epsilon(s = 0) = \hat{\epsilon}(s = 1)$, $\epsilon(s = 1) = \hat{\epsilon}(s = 0)$. When $1 \gg q$ -the thin-shell limit- ϵ is independent of s ; when $q = 1$ we get the two-phase, doubly coated-sphere configuration. Here again, for q fixed at 1, the models with $0 \leq s \leq 1$ cover the whole allowed range of the effective ϵ .

When we consider two (uncoupled) linear-response constants, say ϵ and μ , of the same composite, the models of this sort, with $0 \leq s \leq 1$, fill a certain area in the ϵ - μ plane. The two-parameter model is thus helpful in examining simultaneous bounds on two effective constants^{2,3,10}. Schulgasser¹¹, for example, had employed hierarchical models to probe such simultaneous bounds.

III. FORMALISM: GENERALIZATION TO MULTIFIELD PHENOMENA

We now develop the formalism for calculating the effective constants of the layered-shell model and we do this for the general linear-response problem involving n coupled driving fields, derivable from potentials, which we shall treat as an n -tuple: $\varphi = (\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_n)$. The conjugate currents $\vec{J} = (\vec{J}_1, \vec{J}_2, \dots, \vec{J}_n)$ are linear in the potentials and given by

$$\vec{J}(\vec{r}) = -L(\vec{r}) \vec{\nabla} \varphi(\vec{r}) \quad (12)$$

Here L is the response matrix, generalizing ϵ .

In our multicomponent model, L is piecewise constant, taking the value L_k in the shell S_k . The potentials satisfy the n coupled equations

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{J} = \vec{\nabla} \cdot (L \vec{\nabla} \varphi) = 0. \quad (13)$$

For a medium in which L is piecewise constant—such as ours—the potentials satisfy the Laplace equation within each component; across boundaries, φ and the normal component of \vec{J} are continuous. As described in §II, we want to calculate the response matrix, L , of the equivalent medium—one that is oblivious to the embedding of our shell system (with the effective medium filling the central cavity, as well). We then look for a solution of the field equations (13) with homogeneous fields, $\vec{\nabla} \varphi_k$, outside the shells. Without loss of generality, we choose all these fields in the same direction for all the fields—the polar z -axis. The φ -dependence cannot change across the spherical boundaries and so we must have, everywhere,

$$\varphi(\vec{r}) = \vartheta(r) \cos \theta. \quad (14)$$

The most general behavior possible for $\vartheta(r)$ within S_k (for φ to satisfy the Laplace equation) is

$$\vartheta(r) = a_k r + \hat{b}_k r^{-d'}, \quad (15)$$

where a_k and b_k are n -tuplets of constants, and $d' = d - 1$. The continuity of ϑ across r_k requires:

$$a_k + b_k = a_{k+1} + b_{k+1} \zeta_{k+1}. \quad (16)$$

Here we have put $b_k \equiv \hat{b}_k r_k^{-d}$ and $\zeta_{k+1} \equiv r_{k+1}^d / r_k^d$.

The continuity of J_r across r_k reads:

$$L_k (a_k - d' b_k) = L_{k+1} (a_{k+1} - d' \zeta_{k+1} b_{k+1}). \quad (17)$$

In terms of the $2n$ -tuplets of coefficients $u_k \equiv (a_k, b_k)$ eqs. (16) (17) can be written as

$$A_k u_k = A_{k+1} Z_{k+1} u_{k+1}, \quad (18)$$

where, A_k is a $2n \times 2n$ matrix:

$$A_k \equiv \begin{pmatrix} I & I \\ L_k & -d' L_k \end{pmatrix}; \quad (19)$$

with I , the $n \times n$ unit matrix; and, Z_{k+1} is the diagonal matrix

$$Z_{k+1} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & \zeta_{k+1} I \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

We seek a solution for which $b_{p+1} = 0$, or $u_{p+1} = (a_{p+1}, 0)$. The field coefficients in the central hollow, u_0 , are then related to those outside the shell system, u_{p+1} , by

$$u_0 = Au_{p+1} \equiv A_0^{-1} A_1 Z_1 A_1^{-1} A_2 Z_2 \dots A_p^{-1} A_{p+1} u_{p+1} \quad (21)$$

(with the last factor of Z_{p+1} justifiably dropped for the above form of u_{p+1}). The matrices A_k are easily inverted to give

$$A_k^{-1} = d^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} d' & L_k^{-1} \\ 1 & -L_k^{-1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

Equation (21) can also be written as

$$u_0 = A_0^{-1} B_1 B_2 \dots B_p A_{p+1} u_{p+1}, \quad (23)$$

With

$$B_k \equiv A_k Z_k A_k^{-1} = d^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} d + \eta_k & -\eta_k L_k^{-1} \\ -d' & \eta_k L_k^{-1} + d' \end{pmatrix} \quad (24)$$

Here $\eta_k \equiv \zeta_k^{-1} = v_k q (r_p^d / r_{k-1}^d)$.

The transmission matrix, A , defined in eq. (21), is a function of the L_k 's, of q , of the volume fractions (through the η_k 's), and of L ; the latter being determined by requiring that the potentials are regular at the origin; i.e., that $b_0 = 0$, for any choice of a_{p+1} . Dividing A into quarters:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} A^{11} & A^{12} \\ A^{21} & A^{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

we require, then, that $n \times n$ submatrix A^{21} vanish. For a system made of one set of shells, encapsulating the effective medium, and embedded in it, we have

$$A_0 = A_{p+1} = \begin{pmatrix} I & I \\ L & -d'L \end{pmatrix} \quad (26)$$

Writing then

$$B \equiv B_1 B_2 \dots B_p = \begin{pmatrix} B^{11} & B^{12} \\ B^{21} & B^{22} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (27)$$

we get $A^{21} \propto B^{11} - L^{-1} B^{21} + B^{12} L - L^{-1} B^{22} L = 0$, or finally,

$$L B^{12} L + L B^{11} - B^{22} L - B^{21} = 0, \quad (28)$$

This is the equation for the effective response matrix, of the d -dimensional layered-shell model. It is a coupled quadratic equation in the elements of L ; the B^{ij} 's are matrix-valued, rational functions of the L_k 's—the response matrices of the components.

One may ask at this point whether a legitimate solution—one in which L is real, symmetric, and positive-definite—always exists. Equation (28) is a set of n^2 equations but there are only the $n(n+1)/2$ independent elements of L as unknowns. We shall come back to this question in §V.

We note that the submatrix A^{11} of A plays the role of the shielding matrix for the

shell system giving the field strengths in the cavity in terms of those outside the system: $a_0 = A^{11} a_{p+1}$. The shielding matrix is given by

$$A^{11} = d^{-1} (L^{-1} B_{L+L}^{22} + L^{-1} B^{21} + d' B^{12} + d' B^{11}), \quad (29)$$

or, eliminating the first two, or the last two terms, by use of eq.(28) we get

$$A^{11} = B^{11} + B^{12} L = L^{-1} (B^{21} + B^{22} L). \quad (30)$$

After ℓ nesting steps the fields are reduced by $(A^{11})^\ell$.

We now consider the two limiting models with $1 \gg q$, and $q=1$. From the definition of η_k [below eq. (24)] we see that $\eta_k = v_k q + O(q^2)$. Retaining only the lowest order in q we find from eq. (24)

$$B_k \approx I_{2n} + qd^{-1} v_k \begin{pmatrix} I & -L_k^{-1} \\ -d' L_k & d' I \end{pmatrix}, \quad (31)$$

and to the same order

$$B = \prod_{k=1}^p B_k \approx I_{2n} + qd^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^p v_k \begin{pmatrix} I & -L_k^{-1} \\ -d' L_k & d' I \end{pmatrix}. \quad (32)$$

Here, I_{2n} is the $2n \times 2n$ unit matrix. Defining the mean, M , and harmonic-mean, H , of the L_k 's:

$$M \equiv \sum_{k=1}^p v_k L_k; \quad H \equiv \left(\sum_{k=1}^p v_k L_k^{-1} \right)^{-1}, \quad (33)$$

we have

$$B \approx I_{2n} + qd^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} I & -H^{-1} \\ -d' M & d' I \end{pmatrix}. \quad (34)$$

Identifying the quarter submatrices of B and using eq. (28), we get, to lowest order in q ,

$$LH^{-1}L + (d-2)L - (d-1)M = 0, \quad (35)$$

as the equation for the effective response matrix of the thin-shells composite—a generalization of eq. (7) to the multifield problem. Note that M and H —and hence L —are invariant under a permutation of any of the shells (each keeping its thickness). Note also that M and H are symmetric and positive-definite matrices—as are all the L_k 's. We shall show in § V that eq.(35) always has a unique, real, symmetric, and positive-definite solution.

The shielding matrix for this case can be obtained by substituting the B^{ij} 's from eq. (31) into eq. (30):

$$A^{11} = I - \frac{qd'}{d} (L^{-1} M - I) + O(q^2) = I - \frac{q}{d} (H^{-1} L - I) + O(q^2). \quad (36)$$

We shall show in § V that its eigenvalues are not larger than 1.

We now turn to the case $q=1$ which corresponds to $r_0=0$. One can get the equation for L , in this case, by taking the limit $r_0 \rightarrow 0$, in eq.(28). It is, however, easier to re-derive this equation by replacing A_0^{-1} with A_1^{-1} , as the first factor on the right-hand-side of eq.(21)-this corresponds to filling the central cavity with component 1, instead of the trial medium-and requiring, as before, that the lower-left quarter of the resulting transmission matrix vanish. This matrix is now given by $A_1^{-1}B_2 \dots B_p A_{p+1}$ into which L enters only through A_{p+1} . The resulting equation is thus linear in L -in contrast with the general, $q \neq 1$, case. If we write

$$\hat{B} = B_2 \dots B_p = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{B}^{11} & \hat{B}^{12} \\ \hat{B}^{21} & \hat{B}^{22} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (37)$$

we get $\hat{B}^{11} - L^{-1}\hat{B}^{21} + (\hat{B}^{12} - L^{-1}\hat{B}^{22})L = 0$ or

$$L = (\hat{B}^{22} - L^{-1}\hat{B}^{12})^{-1} (L^{-1}\hat{B}^{11} - \hat{B}^{21}). \quad (38)$$

This is the explicit expression for the effective response matrix for a multifield linear-response in a multicoated-sphere composite-a special case of the multicomponent-shell model.

Sihvola and Lindel^{17,18} use similar transmission-matrix methods to solve for the effective constant of a multicoated-sphere configuration for the single-field case.

IV. EXAMPLES: TWO-COMPONENT MODELS

Substituting the expressions for B_1, B_2 from eq. (24) in eq. (27) and using eq. (28) we write the general equation for the effective response matrix, L , of a two-component, layered-shell model:

$$LK_1L + K_2L + LK_3 + kL + K_4 = 0, \quad (39)$$

where,

$$K_1 = (d + \eta_1) \eta_2 L_2^{-1} + \eta_1 (d + d' \eta_2) L_1^{-1}; \quad (40)$$

$$K_2 = \eta_1 \eta_2 d' L_1 L_2^{-1}; \quad (41)$$

$$K_3 = -\eta_1 \eta_2 d' L_1^{-1} L_2; \quad (42)$$

$$k = d(d-2)(\eta_1 + \eta_2 + \eta_1 \eta_2); \quad (43)$$

$$K_4 = -\eta_1 d' (d + \eta_2) L_1 - \eta_2 d' (d + d' \eta_1) L_2 = 0. \quad (44)$$

Here, η_1, η_2 are given in terms of q and the volume fractions by

$$\eta_1 = \frac{v_1 q}{1-q}, \quad \eta_2 = \frac{v_2 q}{1-v_2 q} \quad (45)$$

There is special interest in the effective response matrix of a two-component coated-sphere model, especially because they define bounds on the allowed values of the effective coefficients. In this ($p=2$) case (with component 2 outside), $\hat{B} = B_2$ and the quarter

submatrices of \hat{B} can be read off eq. (24). Noting that $\eta_2 = (r_2^d - r_1^d) / r_1^d = v_2 / v_1$, we find

$$L_{CS} = \left\{ v_2 L_2^{-1} + (v_1 + d') L_1^{-1} \right\}^{-1} (v_2 d' L_1^{-1} L_2 + v_1 d + v_2), \quad (46)$$

for the response matrix of a coated-sphere model with component 2 outside. When only one field is involved, equation (46) reduces to the well-known single-field result.

V. REPRESENTATION OF THE PROBLEM IN THE EIGENBASIS

It has been shown¹⁹ that the multifield, linear-response process of a two-component composite can be described in some eigenbasis of potentials and currents, $\psi = (\psi_1, \psi_2, \dots, \psi_n)$ and $\vec{J} = (\vec{J}_1, \vec{J}_2, \dots, \vec{J}_n)$, respectively, that are totally decoupled; these are, respectively, linear combinations of the "physical" fields φ and \vec{J} . The argument is based on the fact that any two real, symmetric, positive-definite matrices (of the same rank) can be diagonalized simultaneously by a real, congruent transformation: There exists a matrix W such that

$$\begin{aligned} W L_1 \tilde{W} &= \lambda^{(1)} \equiv \text{diag}(\lambda_1^{(1)}, \lambda_2^{(1)}, \dots, \lambda_n^{(1)}); \\ W L_2 \tilde{W} &= \lambda^{(2)} \equiv \text{diag}(\lambda_1^{(2)}, \lambda_2^{(2)}, \dots, \lambda_n^{(2)}). \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

The eigenfields are then

$$\psi = \tilde{W}^{-1} \phi, \quad \vec{J} = W \vec{J}, \quad (48)$$

and one has

$$\vec{J} = -\lambda^{(1)} \vec{\nabla} \psi, \quad \text{and} \quad \vec{J} = -\lambda^{(2)} \vec{\nabla} \psi, \quad (49)$$

in components 1 and 2, respectively. Milgrom and Shtrikman¹⁹ use the existence of this basis to derive compatibility conditions, on the response matrix of any two-phase composite, that require no knowledge of the volume fractions or the microstructure of the composite. For an isotropic composite, such as the one we discuss in this paper, the relation is

$$L L_1^{-1} L_2 = L_2 L_1^{-1} L \quad (50)$$

Here, we can use the eigenbasis for the following purposes-pertinent to two-phase shell composites: (i) To show that there exists a physical solution to the equation for L . (ii) To show that the shielding matrix has eigenvalues that are not larger than unity. (iii) To demonstrate that all the multifield results we have derived for two-shell composite, can be obtained, straightforwardly, from the single-field result.

When working in the eigenbasis of the two-phase composite, L_1, L_2 are everywhere replaced by the $\lambda^{(1)}, \lambda^{(2)}$. As all the B^{ij} 's appearing in § III are rational functions of the L_k 's, they are also diagonal in the eigenbasis, and so are the matrix coefficients K_i in eq. (39). Multiplying eq. (39) by W on the left, and \tilde{W} on the right and defining $k_1 \equiv \tilde{W}^{-1} K_1 W^{-1}$, $k_2 \equiv W K_2 W^{-1}$, $k_3 \equiv \tilde{W}^{-1} K_3 \tilde{W}$, $k_4 \equiv W K_4 \tilde{W}$, and $\lambda \equiv W L \tilde{W}$, we get

$$\lambda k_1 \lambda + k_2 \lambda + \lambda k_3 + k_4 \lambda = 0, \quad (51)$$

with the k_i 's all diagonal.

Now, since L_1 and L_2 are positive definite, eqs.(40)-(44) tell us that k_1 is positive and k_4 is negative. There is then always a solution, λ , of the matrix equation (51) that is diagonal and positive; hence, the original equation (39) always has a solution L that is real, symmetric, and positive-definite as is required from a response matrix.

The many-component composite does not, in general, have an eigenbasis of decoupled fields. The many-component, thin-shell model is, nonetheless, amenable to an attack similar to the above: The matrices M and H which enter eq. (35) are linear combinations of symmetric, positive-definite matrices and thus share the same properties. They can, then, be diagonalized simultaneously by a congruent transformation into $m \equiv W M \tilde{W}$, $h \equiv W H \tilde{W}$ (the L_k 's themselves are not diagonalized by W , in the general, $p > 2$, case). It is easy to see, in the same way as above, that eq. (35) always has a legitimate solution:

$$L = W^{-1} \left\{ \frac{h}{2} \left(\sqrt{(d-2)^2 + 4(d-1) m h^{-1}} - 1 \right) \right\} \tilde{W}^{-1}. \quad (52)$$

The shielding matrix is also diagonal in the eigenbasis; it is, in fact, diagonalized by the similarity transformation:

$$a^{11} \equiv \tilde{W}^{-1} A^{11} \tilde{W}, \quad (53)$$

and so the elements of a^{11} are the eigenvalues of A^{11} . The elements m_k, h_k, λ_k of m, h, λ , respectively, are not, in general, the eigenvalues of M, H, L , as the former are not obtained from the latter by a similarity transformation. However, the elements of diagonal matrices like $m h^{-1}, h^{-1} \lambda$ etc. are the eigenvalues of the corresponding matrices in the physical basis; these do transform by similarity. Note that the response matrices connect potential to fluxes, and hence transform by congruence; the shielding matrix and the like connect potentials to potentials, and transform by similarity. Now because M and H are, respectively, the mean and harmonic mean of symmetric, positive-definite matrices, one can show that.

$$n_k \leq \lambda_k \leq m_k, \quad (54)$$

and so

$$a^{11} = I - \frac{q}{d} (h^{-1} \lambda - I) \leq I, \quad (55)$$

and so the eigenvalues of A^{11} that is given in eq. (36) are not larger than unity. We can also prove that this is true for the general case with $1 \leq q$ and two components only. We suspect that the statement is true, in general, but cannot offer a proof.

All the results we derived for the two-phase case can also be derived by writing a known, single-field result for the eigenfields and transforming back to the physical basis. In general, take any result that is valid for the single-field, two-phase case constituting an equality or an inequality involving the constants of the components and of the mixture; if this result holds for all the eigenfields, it can be written as a diagonal-matrix-relation. This relation has then to be written such as to have, on each side, an expression of the form... $\lambda^a (\lambda^b)^{-1} \lambda^c (\lambda^d)^{-1}$..., where the λ 's are the diagonal response matrices in the eigenbasis, all of which transform in the same way. The same relation then holds in the physical basis, with the λ 's replaced by the L 's. As an example, we rederive the expression for the coated sphere model, for the multi-field case. The well known expression for the effective constant ϵ is written, in three dimensions, as

$$\epsilon = \left\{ v_2 \epsilon_2^{-1} + (2+v_1) \epsilon_1^{-1} \right\}^{-1} (2v_2 \epsilon_1^{-1} \epsilon_2 + 3v_1 + v_2). \quad (56)$$

In the multifield case, this holds for each eigenfield separately and so it holds as a matrix expression with the ϵ 's replaced by the diagonal λ 's. Now, multiplying by W on the left and by \tilde{W} on the right, we get the same equation for the L 's, and this gives eq.(46) The form in which the right-hand-side of eq.(56) is put allows us to insert the appropriate W^{-1} factors, so that each λ is transformed into its corresponding L .

The same is true for inequalities; but they are understood as applying between quadratic forms, when the matrices in question are symmetric-expressing the fact that some matrix is positive definite. Alternatively, as the case may be, the matrix inequality is to be understood as applying to the eigenvalues. For example, if we show that the shielding factor $\sigma \leq 1$, in the single-field case, it follows that the shielding matrix is not larger than I -in the sense that its eigenvalues are not larger than unity-As A^{11} and I transform in the same way as we go from the eigenbasis to the physical basis.

It is known¹ that the single-field, coated-sphere, effective constants constitute bounds on the effective constants of a two-phase mixture; does the multifield result, eq. (46), play a similar role? Here the situation is not so simple. Which of the two coated spheres (with component 1 inside or outside) is the upper bound and which the lower one, depends on which of the two components has the larger constant. In the multifield case, it is possible that for some of the eigenfields, one component has larger constants and for the other eigenfields the other does; we can then not write a simple matrix inequality in the eigenbasis. If, however, we have two components for which $L_2 - L_1$ has a definite sign, as a quadratic form-say it is positive definite-then it follows that L_{CS} given in eq. (46) is an upper bound to the response matrix, L , of any composite made of components 1 and 2, in the sense that $L_{CS} - L$ is nonnegative; eq. (46) gives the lower bound, in the same sense, when 1 and 2 are interchanged.

VI. CONCLUDING REMARKS

We have derived the expression for the effective response matrix of a novel model for isotropic composites. The general problem of linear-response to n coupled driving fields, and p components, in d dimensions have been treated. All our results are valid for complex response matrices^{20,21}. This family of models arise as a natural generalization of the muchdiscussed, coated- and multicoated-sphere models. The effective response matrix for the multifield case has not been given before, even for the latter, and is derived in this paper as a special case. Further extension to spaced-out shells is not possible; but, one can, as always, incorporate the shell model in any hierarchical scheme to form more complex composite models.

For example, we can build a hierarchical composite based on the thin-shell model, by beginning with a pure material-say component 2-and add to it an small increment of 1 to form a thin shell composite; this is then used with another increment of 1 to form a thin-shell composite. Continuing in this manner in a well known procedure (a detailed-but by no means the first-account is given in ref. 22) we obtain in the limit of infinitesimal increments, a differential equation that gives the effective constant, ϵ , of the composite, for a finite volume fraction of 1:

$$\frac{dx}{dV} = - \frac{(x-1)(x+d')}{Vd'} \quad (57)$$

where, $x \equiv \epsilon / \epsilon_1$ and V is the total volume; the former is to be integrated between ϵ_2 / ϵ_1 and ϵ / ϵ_1 , and the latter between V_2 and $V_1 + V_2$. Integrating eq. (57) we find, rather interestingly the coated-sphere expression for ϵ . Thus, beginning with one component and adding the other continuously we get a composite with the maximal and minimal allowed values of ϵ -those realized by the two possible coated-sphere configurations, here realized by hierarchical thin-shell models. Clearly, by alternating the component we add incrementally, we can obtain an hierarchical, thin-shell model for any value between

the bounds, for given volume fractions: any isotropic composite is realizable by a thin-shell model composite.

composites made of planar laminates have received much warranted attention^{8,9,12}, and, in fact, play the role of a basic building-block of model composites. The thin-shell layered-shell models are akin to these and, presumably, can play similar roles. Like planar laminates, they have an effective response matrix that is invariant to an interchange of any of the layers. An advantage of the shell models is their built-in isotropy; it frees one from having to isotropize the laminate model when an isotropic model is sought.

All our results can be extended to ellipsoidal shells-delimited by confocal ellipsoids-to describe anisotropic composites²³. Some results that are useful for this end can be found in refs. 24, 21.

Another extension that invites further treatment is the derivation of the effective elastic properties of the shell models-for example, as exactly solvable models for fiber composites⁶.

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Figure captions

Figure 1. The schematics of a single shell-system.

Figure 2. The filling of space with basic shell systems to give the effective composite. The two components are represented by black and white, and the portions of space that are not yet filled, with an intermediate shade.

Figure 3. A specific sequence of space-filling by concentric nesting, that reproduces Schulgasser's model of isotropized polycrystals in which the crystal grains are arranged in solid spheres. The shades are of the same signification as in Fig. 2.

Figure 4. The extension of Schulgasser's model to a polycrystalline shell model. Crystalline grains of a uniaxial crystal are arranged in spherical shells so that the symmetry axis of each is along the radius of the shell in which it resides. Shells are then nested within shells in an infinite sequence.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.